

Pachypodium namaquanum

Halfmens

© T Makola

Group: Eudicot

Size: 1-3.5 meters.

Distribution:

This species occurs in the Northern Cape where it is found in Pella and Steinkopf and extends to southern Namibia where it occurs from Rosh Pinah to near Goodhouse.

Importance:

These trees are said in Nama folklore to be people turned into plants, forever facing north toward their lost homeland. *Pachypodium namaquanum* is highly poisonous and difficult to grow outside the Richtersveld. Though seeds germinate easily, it rarely survives in cultivation and is legally protected, making it rare in gardens.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 66.68 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 23.13 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.91 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.8% [Single: 96.0%, Duplicated: 2.8%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 87 860.79 kilobases
Contig number: 539

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